

ASSESSMENT OF PRECIPITATION CHANGES USING MULTIPLE GENERAL CIRCULATION MODELS OVER THE GAMBIA

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ABSTRACT

Gambia is the smallest nation on the African mainland, covering 10,690 square kilometers. The natural resources and environment have been heavily affected by changes in climate, such as shifts in temperature and rainfall, which have negatively impacted the growth cycles of crops, their production, and the regrowth of forests. This study uses projected changes in precipitation downscaled statistically from three general circulation models (GCMs): the Max Planck Institute of Meteorology (MPI-ESM), the National Centre for Meteorological Research (CNRM-CM5), and the Canadian Centre for Climate Modelling and Analysis (CanESM5) under two representative concentration pathways (RCP 8.5 and 4.5). The study uses spatial and statistical metrics to determine the impact of climate change on projected precipitation in the study area from 2030 to 2060. The RCP 8.5 scenario forecasts annual precipitation reductions of 35.7%, 32.5%, and 25.6%, whereas the RCP 4.5 projects decreases of 33.4%, 29.2%, and 20.4% for CanEM5, MPI-ESM, and CNRM-CM5 by 2030-2060. Thus, the decline will likely lead to a decline in crop yield by 20.4% and 25.8% under the RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 in The Gambia. Attaining food sufficiency and security becomes increasingly complicated and unrealistic. Thus, accelerated strategic climate actions such as the implementation of Climate Smart Agriculture (CSA), which includes integrated irrigation and the adoption of highly drought-resistant crops, need to be implemented by government and other stakeholders.

Keywords: Climate change, Precipitation, General Circulation Models, Representative Concentration Pathways, The Gambia

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INTRODUCTION

The Gambia falls into the tropical sub-humid eco-climatic zone, with an annual rainfall of 800–1200 mm. High humidity and temperatures that average between 27°C and 30°C are characteristics of the rainy season,

which runs from June to October. Temperatures between 24°C and 27°C are cooler during the dry season, which runs from November to May. The dry season results in the most extreme heat inland, with daytime highs of around 40°C (Weather-Atlas, 2024). Sea breezes provide cooling benefits to coastal regions, resulting in more consistent, year-round temperatures (Weather-Atlas, 2024). The gravest human-induced disturbance of the ecosystems and productive systems is global warming and climate change across the world (Cruz-Gonzalez et al., 2021). The simulations of climate models reveal that the average temperatures may increase by 3-4.5degC by the middle of the 21st century to 2100 with higher levels of evapotranspiration and lower levels of precipitation (GOTG, 2023). The Gambia is found to be very vulnerable to the effects of climate, especially the rise in sea-level. The use of local data in four Global Circulation Models predicts variable outcomes and annual rainfall projections have ranged between 29% and 59% of available data (GOTG, 2003). The projected climate over the Gambia could alter the hydrologic balance and thus lead to serious food and water insecurity and also push more people to extreme poverty if accelerated mitigation strategies are not urgently deployed. Bakele et al. (2019) found that climate change may impact hydrological processes by adjusting local climate conditions, which would lead to decrease precipitation and more drought episodes.

Observable alterations in the global water cycle have been a part of human-caused climate change since the mid-1900s (Arias et al., 2021). According to the IPCC's Sixth Assessment Report from 2021, these changes will only intensify on a regional and global scale (Arias et al., 2021). Additionally, the report discovered that: during 1950, precipitation has increased across land, and during the 1980s, the pace of increase has accelerated in higher latitudes. The global hydrological cycle will undoubtedly be accelerated, increased, or changed as a result of global warming. Therefore, it is projected that extreme weather events like drought and heavy rain would become more frequent in the future; the wet regions will become even more humid, and the dry regions will become much drier (IPCC, 2013).

Hence, understanding the complexity of climate change effects on the hydrological cycle is highly significant for projecting rainfall variability for integrated water resources management and allocation. Since the effects of climate change have become more severe globally, it is critical to comprehend future changes, especially at regional scales, in order to design adaptation and mitigation strategies (Bouwer, 2011). Understanding the degree of uncertainty in the hydrological response at the regional scale as well as how hydrological processes are anticipated to alter is therefore crucial (Dessu, & Melesse, 2013). Therefore, there is a need to assess likely climate change effects on precipitation over the Gambia to develop robust adaptation strategies. Climate models are dynamic tools that apply the laws of physics and thermodynamics to simulate historical climate and project future climatic datasets. Mifsud-Scicluna and Galdies (2025) found that General Circulation Models (GCMs) are crucial for projecting climate conditions at seasonal and regional levels, whereas Deepthi and Sivakumar (2022) indicated that climate models are sophisticated tools used in climate studies for predicting the future climate.

In this regard, the paper attempts to evaluate the effects of global warming on future precipitation trends using a collection of general circulation models taking the representative concentration pathway scenarios, RCP 8.5 and RCP 4.5 respectively. The chosen GCM models from the archive of CMIP 5 were based on their capacities to reproduce historical and projected climate variables over the African continent as revealed by several studies (Ahmadalipour et al., 2017; Shahab et al., 2020). Hence, the anticipated findings from the study will provide a projected database for precipitation in the region, which will be useful to policymakers in developing climate mitigation strategies for sustainable water resource management and addressing persistent food insecurity in The Gambia.

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

The Gambia is a country situated in West Africa. It is located on the Atlantic coast and has a border with Senegal. The region comprises an elongated, narrow expanse of land encircling the Gambia River. The river, which spans almost the whole length of the country, dominates the flat terrain. The Gambia extends approximately 300 miles (480 km) inland, consisting of a land strip 15 to 30 miles (25 to 50 km) wide adjacent to the Gambia River, as illustrated in Figure 1. It lies between latitudes of 13deg 26 44.83 N and 15deg 18 22.04 W and occupies an elevation of 17 meters above the sea level. The Gambia is a tropical climate with a lengthy dry season and a growth rainy period that normally falls in the months of June to October. The study location is shown in table 1.

Figure 1: Map of the Gambia as Completely Surrounded by Senegal

Source: Weather-Atlas, 2024

Table 1: Location of Study Region

Regions	Code	Coordinates	
Banjul	BJL	13.4519 N	16.6645E
Central River Region	CRR	13.5994N	14.8922E
North Bank Region	NBR	13.5285N	16.017E
Lower River Region	LRR	13.3553N	15.923E
Upper River Region	URR	13.4257N	14.0072E
West Coast Region	WCR	13.2229N	16.582E

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The Gambia is characterised as a semi-arid region with a longer period of the dry season from October through June, with three months of the rainy season. Average annual precipitation and temperature spatially vary over the provinces, with Basse Santa Su having an estimated temperature of 20°C and precipitation of 1000 mm, while Yundum records about 1300 mm. The relative humidity decreases from December through April, with the lowest in January and the highest of about 85% in August.

GCM ensemble selection

Selection of appropriate GCMs is significant for climate studies over the study region and thus improves the quality of climate projection and provides robust insight for policymakers to develop effective strategies for mitigating climate change. It is important to select multiple general circulation models in climate studies so that the outcomes of the projections for each GCM can be compared to evaluate and measure their degree of relationship and correlation. The capacity and validity of GCMs to accurately reproduce historical climate observations should be the primary consideration when choosing them. Mendlik and Gobiet (2016) revealed that the selection of GCMs should be primarily based on their validity for simulating historical climates. Thober and Samaniego (2014) once again suggested that effective replication of baseline temperature and precipitation could contribute to the accuracy of general circulation models. Therefore, the selected GCMs for this study were based on their capacities to reproduce historical climate as detailed in the archive of CMIP5 over the African continent. The approach is consistent with the methodology described by Ragetti *et al.* (2013) and Xie *et al.* (2013), which explain that model selection is based on their replicating capacity for historical climate conditions. A table detailing the combination of three chosen climate models to be used in this research in the mentioned climate change emission scenarios is given in Table 2. RCP 4.5 is a moderate emission pathway; however, RCP 8.5 is a high-emission worst-case climatic change pathway (Meinshausen *et al.*, 2011; Pielke, 2021). The comparison of projected climate changes is made in terms of the mid-term (2030-2060) period in comparison to the period of 1985-2015 which is considered a baseline period.

Table 2: Selected General Circulation Models

Model Institute	Model name	Country	Resolution
National Centre for Scientific Experiments	CNRM-ESM2-1	France	1.25° × 2.5°
Planck Meteorological Institute, Germany	MPI-ESM2-0	Germany	0.93° × 0.93°
Centre for Climate Modeling and Analysis, Canada	CanESM5	Canada	2.81° × 2.81°

Source: IPCC, 2013

Climate Database

The historical daily precipitation data were extracted from 25 weather stations located across the provinces of the Gambia between 1985 and 2015. The methodology explained by Mahyun et al. (2023) was used to estimate the missing data as shown in equation I:

$$P_X = \frac{\frac{P_A + P_B + P_C}{(dX_A)^2 + (dX_B)^2 + (dX_C)^2}}{\frac{1}{(dX_A)^2} + \frac{1}{(dX_B)^2} + \frac{1}{(dX_C)^2}} \quad (I)$$

Where is PA, PB, PC Px precipitation data in stations A, B, C.

Model Validation

Projecting future precipitation under various climate change scenarios, it is important to justify the capability of ensemble GCMs to simulate the referenced precipitation using a set of validation statistics. The efficacy of the Statistically Downscaling Method (SDSM) in replicating the baseline was assessed through bias-corrected values by juxtaposing the downscaled climate derived from large-scale predictors with station-observed precipitation from 1985 to 2015 for the study area (Wilby and Dawson, 2014). Spatial correlation coefficients (COR), MAE, and root RMSE are extensively applied to evaluate CMIP 5 models' simulations (Su et al., 2016), as indicated in equations II-IV.

$$CORR = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (X_{obsi} - \bar{x}_{obs})(X_{simi} - \bar{x}_{sim})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (X_{simi} - \bar{x}_{sim})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (X_{simi} - \bar{x}_{sim})^2}} \quad (II)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (Clim_{sim} - Clim_{obs})^2} \quad (III)$$

$$MAE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (Clim_{sim} - Clim_{obs})^2 \quad (IV)$$

Where;

Xobsi/Climobs is the ith observed climate (precipitation), Xsimi/Climsim is the ith GCM, N is the dataset number, I is the monthly test, Pfacj is the precipitation correction factor, Prec is the precipitation, and J, f, and d are for January, February, and December, respectively, while the simulated climate is N, i is the month of the test dataset. Pfacj is the correction factor for the precipitation (Prec) in the months of January (j), February (f), and December (d), while Pfaca is the annual climate anomaly.

Future Precipitation Projections

The monthly climate variable (precipitation) variances in response to the baseline period were projected over the study region. Trink et al. (2013) approach was used to estimate changes in future climate. To compute future changes in climatic variables, for each month (January to December), a climate change correction factor was computed as given in equations V and VI. This correcting factor is a representative of the anomaly from the baseline period (1985-2015) and the near term (2030-2060). Trink et al. (2013) assumption that the correction factor occurs linearly in time was used to determine the annual correction factor. Therefore, projected changes in precipitation (Prec) for the chosen GCM were estimated as expressed in equation VII.

$$P_{\text{facj}} = \frac{A_{\text{nj}}}{P_{\text{rec}}} \quad (\text{V})$$

$$P_{\text{faca}} = \frac{A_{\text{nj}}}{P_{\text{recj}}} + \frac{A_{\text{nf}}}{P_{\text{recf}}} + \frac{A_{\text{nm}}}{P_{\text{recm}}} \dots \dots \dots \frac{A_{\text{nd}}}{P_{\text{recd}}} \quad (\text{VI})$$

$$PF_{(\text{Near_Term})} = PR_i + (PR_i * [Y_{2030-2060} - Y_{1985-2015}]) * P_{\text{faca}} \quad (\text{VII})$$

Where;

P_{facj} is the correction factor for the precipitation (Prec) in (j), (f), and (d). A_{nj} is the monthly climate anomaly, P_{faca} is the annual climate anomaly, and PF is the future precipitation (mm) for near (2030-2060).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Model Calibration and Evaluation

The selection of GCMs is based on their capacity to replicate historical precipitation, as indicated by R^2 , RMSE, and MBE values, which compare simulated and observed monthly mean precipitation datasets, as shown in Table 2. The best-performing model was ranked as CNRM-CM5, showing the lowest values of MAE and RMSE with the strongest positive values of r and r^2 , while the second- and third-best-performing models were ranked as MPI-ESM and CanESM5, as shown in Table 3. The results presented in Table III showed that the ensemble GCMs demonstrate a strong capacity for reproducing historical precipitation; this performance could be considered appropriate for using the selected models to project future precipitation under the chosen climate change scenarios. The results showed similarity with the finding of Enyew et al. (2024), which revealed that the highest-performing climate models for replicating historical climate indicated the lowest MAE, RMSE, and bias values in all the agro-ecological zones. Again, the finding from the study of Zebaze *et al.* (2025) further supports the result of this study, which revealed that general circulation models used for this study effectively simulated historical precipitation over the African continent with high correlation with low RMSE and MAE values which are used in climate-model evaluation. Figure 2 depicts the relationship between the simulated and observed precipitation over the study region.

Models	RMSE	CORR (r)	r²	MAE	P-value
CanESM5	0.834	0.989	0.979	8.232	<0.00001
CNRMCM5	0.213	0.995	0.999	5.921	<0.00001
MPI-ESM	0.344	0.993	0.988	7.071	<0.00001

Source: Simulation Output, 2015

Figure 2: Observed and Simulated Monthly Precipitation from 1985-2015 in the Gambia

Source: Field Simulation Output, 2025

Future Precipitation Projections

Figures 2-8 depict the correlation between historical precipitation and the expected precipitation from GCMs for the period 2030–2060 under the chosen RCPs. The trends and behavioural patterns in the projections generally suggest a possible decrease in precipitation for RCPs 4.5 and 8.5. Figure 3a illustrates that the CanES-M5 model estimates substantial reductions in precipitation, whereas the MPI model estimates average annual precipitation of 647.5 mm and 501.3 mm under RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 for 2030–2060 in Banjul. In CRR, LRR, NBR, URR, and WCR, as presented in Figures 4-8, the projected annual precipitation declines under both RCPs (4.5 and 8.5). Precipitation fluctuations are likely to exhibit similar patterns across all provinces in every season and climate change scenario.

Figure 3: Observed and GCMs projected precipitation at Banjul Region for RCP 4.5 a and RCP 8.5 b.

Source: Field simulation output, 2025

Figure 4: Observed and GCMs projected precipitation at CRR Region for RCP 4.5 a and RCP 8.5 b.

Source: Field simulation output, 2025

Figure 5: Observed and GCMs projected precipitation at LRR Region for RCP 4.5 a and RCP 8.5 b

Source: Field simulation output, 2025

Figure 6: Observed and GCMs projected precipitation at NBR Region for RCP 4.5 a and RCP 8.5 b.

Source: Field simulation output, 2025

Figure 7: Observed and GCMs projected precipitation at URR Region for RCP 4.5 a and RCP 8.5 b.

Source: Field simulation output, 2025

Figure 8: Observed and GCMs projected precipitation at WCR Region for RCP 4.5 a and RCP 8.5 b.

Source: Field simulation output, 2025

The simulation outcomes indicated a potential mild seasonality in certain provinces of the Gambia, as evidenced by the monthly precipitation projections in Figures 3-8. In the Banjul provinces, the MPI and CNRM models estimate early rainfall from March to November, but the CanES-M5 model recorded no precipitation under RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 relative to baseline precipitation events, as presented in Figures 3a-b. Conversely, the projected early rainfall onset of 10.0 mm, 10.4 mm, 5.0 mm, 3.5 mm, 27.1 mm, and 20.6 mm in March, April, and May by MPI during 2030–2060 is insignificant for rainfed agriculture and municipal water storage. The precipitation projection patterns of the LLR, NBR, URR, and WCR regions exhibited similarities to those of the Banjul provinces concerning early precipitation. The early rainfall onset projected by CNRM and CanESM5 also followed the same pattern as the MPI. Therefore, it is generally unacceptable to conduct farming activities during this period without a complete design for full irrigation. Future precipitation forecasts for the Gambia align with the findings of MifsudSciocluna and Galdies (2025), indicating that predominantly coastal regions will experience the most significant reductions in precipitation, ranging from –30 to –85.2% under RCPs 4.5, 6.0, and 8.5 across the three scenarios examined. Stocker et al. (2013) predict that global precipitation would progressively rise, with certain areas likely to experience increases, while some other regions may encounter declines or negligible alterations.

Spatial Distribution of Projected Changes in Precipitation

The predicted changes in annual precipitation in the Gambia under both RCPs and GCMs 4.5 is as shown in Fig. 9. The chosen set of the GCMs indicated a decline in precipitation across most study regions, with projected values ranging from -4.8% to -34.7% according to the MPI model for the period 2030-2060. In CRR, the MPI model projected the lowest change in precipitation at 4.8% and 9.5%, whereas the highest decrease in precipitation at 24.0% and 34.7% was in the West Coast Region (WCR) for RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 for 2030–2060 compared to the historical period of 1985–2015, as depicted in Figure 9. The layer of annual precipitation changes in CNRM and CanESM5 showed strong similarity to the projection of MPI over the study region. Lowest and highest changes in annual precipitation are consistently projected over the CRR and WCR regions, as shown in Fig. IX. Overall, the Gambia will likely experience a decline in precipitation by 2030–2060, resulting in elevated agricultural and meteorological drought conditions and, consequently, yield reductions. This analysis shows similarity with the findings of Bobd et al. (2024), which explained that Madagascar would likely experience a reduction in precipitation in the 21st century with attendant consequences. Similarly, Abiodun et al. (2017) revealed a decrease in rainy days and a future increase in South Africa.

Figure 9: Spatial Distribution of Annual Changes in Precipitation for the RCPs for period 2030-2060 in the Gambia

Source: ARCGIS Simulation Output, 2025

CONCLUSION

This study employed 31 years of monthly historical precipitation data (1985–2015) from fifteen meteorological stations in The Gambia. A collection of GCMs was statistically downscaled to replicate the referenced precipitation, and the models' efficacy in capturing and reproducing the baseline precipitation was assessed using statistical metrics of RMSE, CORR, R², and MAE. The selected general circulation models accurately replicate both monthly and annual baseline precipitation, exhibiting a high degree of confidence and a suitable representation of the specified precipitation events. The study indicates that precipitation projections across all regions under the RCPs for all GCMs demonstrate variable levels of reduction. CanES-M5 forecasts the most substantial reduction in annual mean precipitation, with declines of 36.2% and 39.2% in the West Coast Region (WCR), while the MPI model anticipates the minimal decrease of 4.8% and 9.5% in Banjul during the mid-century period (2030-2060) relative to the reference period (1985-2015) for RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5. The projected decline in precipitation will likely increase the aridity situation in the Gambia, which could lead to an intensive drought and thus result in low food production and the accessibility of safe drinking water. Therefore, it is recommended that the Gambian Ministry of Environment and Water Resources and other policymakers develop effective climate mitigation strategies to provide a robust climate service aimed at climate-smart agriculture, develop drought-resistant crop cultivars, and provide effective climate change advocacy focused on educating farmers, hydrologists, and other stakeholders.

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